

ISic1368

I.Sicily inscription 1368

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140873

1. σὺν θεῷ Χρ (ιστῶ) κ (αὶ) [πατρὶ]
2. αὐτοῦ ἐκοιμ [ήθη]
3. ἡ δούλη τοῦ [θεοῦ]
4. Σαβεΐνα τῆ [πρὸ]
5. τρειῶν εἰδῶν [—]
6. [— — — — — — —]
- 7.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492981

EDCS 39101748

PHI 140873

Bibliography

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